

THE EFFECT OF ATTITUDES, KNOWLEDGE, ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT, REWARDS, AND SKILLS ON JOB INVOLVEMENT OF THE EMPLOYEES OF HIGH-RISK GAS AND OIL INDUSTRY

Jose Cuervo Sababan

Graduate School of Business, San Beda University, Manila, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15071983>

ABSTRACT

The research discusses the influence of attitudes, knowledge, organizational commitment, reward, and competence on job involvement within the oil and gas sector, an emerging sector with limited empirical studies. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational design and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), the research measures quantitatively the degree to which the constructs impact staff engagement. The findings show that organizational commitment ($\beta=0.868$) and rewards ($\beta=0.749$) are the strongest predictors of job involvement, supporting the necessity of encouraging commitment and competitive reward. In contrast, skills ($\beta=-0.22$), knowledge ($\beta=-0.055$), and attitude ($\beta=-0.072$) reveal weak or negative relations, suggesting these might not encourage participation as well. The study is aware of its limitations, i.e., the sample domain being limited to a single firm and applying self-reported approaches, which may impact the external validity of the study findings. However, the outcomes need commitment building, reward system correction, and assignment of challenging work to top performers. The study adds to work commitment in dangerous industries, and the findings can help organizations use it as a source of information for the improvement of employee commitment and performance by using proper human resource practices.

Keywords: *Employee Engagement, Job Involvement, Organizational Commitment, Rewards Systems, KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude, High-Risk Oil and Gas Industries.*

INTRODUCTION

Workers in high-risk industries like the oil and gas industry have seen a massive overhaul due to international crises and pandemics, resulting in gigantic organizational restructuring. The transformation affected the attitude of employees, knowledge, organizational commitment, rewards, and skills, particularly for International Mobile (IM) and International Commuter (IC) workers who had migrated to Saudi Arabia to work. Most of these workers saw considerable cuts in benefits and were confronted with hard options—accepts for lower compensation or termination of employment in the company.

These developments underscore the imperativeness to investigate job involvement in the oil and gas industry, where staff engagement is critical to sustain productivity, safety of operations, and organizational commitment (Demerouti et al., 2017). Employees who were previously used to wonderful benefits-including company sponsored housing, school fees for their kids and yearly vacation excursions-now witnessed compensation shrink as well as decreased benefits. This change can substantially influence their involvement, psychological well-being, and organizational commitment in the long term (Kiazad et al., 2001); less research has specifically examined the influence of these factors on job involvement, particularly in multinational companies working in high risk setting such as Schlumberger in Saudi Arabia. Job engagement, or the degree to which workers associate with and get psychologically engaged in their job (Kanungo, 1982), assumes specific significance under high-stress conditions.

Employees who were previously used to wonderful benefits-including company-sponsored housing, school fees for their kids, and yearly vacation excursions-now witness compensation shrink as well as decreased benefits. This change can substantially influence their job involvement, psychological well-being, and organizational commitment in the long term (Kiazad et al., 2019). Although past literature has taken into account the link between work attitudes and job performance (Judge et al., 2001), less research has specifically examined the influence of these factors on job involvement, particularly in multinational companies working in high-risk settings such as Schlumberger in Saudi Arabia.

The current research seeks to fill this gap through investigation of the part attitudes, knowledge, organizational commitment, rewards, and skills play in job involvement for IM and IC personnel. Because of the pivotal position that workers' engagement in workplace has in work performance and safety, this research is trying to bring information on how organizational management could build strategies that will maximize workers' participation in work and organizational health. Care should be observed on these forces so that there could be sustainable workforce stability in an industry beset by unrelenting economic and structural influences.

Research Objectives

The primary objective of the present study is to examine the extent to which attitudes, knowledge, organizational commitment, rewards, and abilities influence job involvement of employees in the dangerous oil and gas industry, particularly within multinational organizations like Schlumberger in Saudi Arabia. Involvement of employees in these environments is essential for the smoothness of operations and stability of an organization. While previous literature has studied numerous antecedents of job performance and work attitudes, there is a significant gap in the literature concerning their influence on job involvement, particularly for high-stress, high-risk occupations.

In an effort to address this gap, the study tries to seek an answer to the following general research question:

How much do attitudes, knowledge, and organizational commitment, rewards, and skills influence job involvement among gas and oil industry workers?

Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of
 - a. Sex
 - b. Age
 - c. Job level
 - d. Length of service
 - e. Highest educational attainment
2. Assess the level of job involvement among the respondents.
3. Evaluate the effect of the following factors on job involvement:
 - a. Attitude
 - b. Knowledge
 - c. Organizational Commitment
 - d. Rewards
 - e. Skills

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Approach

This research applies the descriptive-correlational research approach with a quantitative method to examine the effect of attitudes, knowledge, organizational commitment, rewards, and skills toward job involvement among the oil and gas sector employees, particularly within a multinational corporation environment at Schlumberger Saudi Arabia. Descriptive is applied in order to give a descriptive analysis of employees' current attitudes towards work, knowledge, skills, organizational commitment, and rewards. This approach would give a thorough explanation of the current conditions without changing the natural setting, necessary to determine patterns and relationships (Sharma, 2019; Nassaji, 2015). The correlational feature of the design seeks to examine the relationships between these variables that is, how they impact the employee job involvement.

Locale and Participants

Research is conducted at Schlumberger Middle East-Asia, in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Using the purposive sampling technique, 30 International Mobile (IM) workers, the supervisors, managers, and rank-and-file-are selected from various departments of the company. Participants are selected based on inclusion criteria such that they represent the broader population of IM employees at the organization. Respondents' profiles include varying demographics and professional background characteristics such as:

- Sex: 96.7% of the respondents are male.
- Age: 56.7% are aged 26 to 30 years.
- Educational Attainment: 80% of them possess a Bachelor's degree.
- Length of Service: 63.3% have served the company 2 to 10 years.
- Employment Position: About 50% of them have been in their current jobs for 1 to 2 years.
- Nationality: Participants consist of Arab (43.3%) and Non-Arab (56.7%) employees with a mix of Roman Catholic (63.3%) and Muslim (10%) participants.
- Employment Status: There is a shift in employment status with 43.3% employed in International Mobile and 46.7% in Home Country Resident positions.

These kinds of demographics and professional details provide an in-depth overview of participants' profiles which are critical to place the findings of the study.

Research Instrument

The data for the research are obtained using a structured survey instruments, which is in the form of a four-point Likert scale questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into two sections: section one captures the demographic information of the respondents, while section two assesses the impact of work attitudes, organizational commitment, rewards, knowledge, and skills on job involvement. The survey instrument as pilot-tested using expert checks and pre-testing. Following this, Cronbach's Alpha reliability test as conducted with a targeted significance of ≤ 0.7 in order to ensure the instrument becomes reliable and consistent.

Data Analysis

In order to analyze the data, descriptive statistics of weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the size of the variables. Additionally, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) as utilized to determine the relationship between the variables. The use of PLS-SEM as due to the fact that it is capable of handling multiple dependent and independent variables simultaneously and model their interaction, direct effect, and indirect effect. This approach provides a suitable model to reflect on the significance of the interactions between work attitudes, organizational commitment, rewards, knowledge, skills, and job involvement.

Data Gathering and Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was taken from all the participants and they were briefed about the research purpose, the procedures, and that they may withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured in all the data, and no personal identifiers were added with the data. The data were kept safely so that there would be no unauthorized access. The research adhered to all the institution and legal ethics guidelines, maintaining the dignity and cultural differences of the participants throughout. Also, participants were allowed not to answer a question that disturbed them. The participants were also presented with an overview of the findings of the study at the end, thus ensuring transparency and respect for their important contribution towards the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of Respondents' Attitudes, Knowledge, Organizational Commitment, Rewards, Job, And Skill

Table 1. *Attitude*

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Factory pays attention to employee attitude.	2.97	0.65	High
2. Work satisfaction is associated with positive attitudes.	3.29	0.61	Very High
3. Judgement by colleagues is important in performance.	2.86	0.59	High
4. Personal relationship with colleagues affects performance.	3.31	0.62	Very High
5. Provide opportunity to spend time working on community activities.	2.63	0.72	High
Overall	3.01	0.64	High

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Low, 1.76-2.50 (Average), 2.51-3.25 (High), 3.260-4.00 (Very High)

A mean rating of 3.01 indicates a high level of agreement in all the statements consistently. Evidence suggests strong concurrence on the significance of "Work satisfaction is associated with positive attitudes" and "Personal relationship with colleagues affects performance," both of which received notably high ratings. Other statements also garnered high rating, signifying an overall prevailing positive attitude among respondents. The moderate standard deviations indicate a moderate level of variability in responses with an overall standard deviation of 0.64.

"Work satisfaction" and "Personal relationships" stand out as strengths with mean values surpassing 3.01; indicate of robust consensus on their positive influence. Conversely, "Attention to employee attitude," "Judgement by colleagues," and "Opportunity for community activities" emerge as areas for improvement with mean values falling below 3.01. The general strength of the overall mean of 3.01 underscores the prevailing positive sentiment.

Table 2. *Knowledge*

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Opportunity for the acquisition of knowledge.	3.29	0.51	Very High

2. Knowledge has a direct influence on performance.	3.40	0.55	Very High
3. Continuous investment in training, and development.	3.23	0.68	High
4. Opportunities to share knowledge.	3.29	0.61	Very High
5. Competence is an important aspect of performance.	3.29	0.56	Very High
Overall	3.30	0.58	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Low), 1.76-2.50 (Average), 2.51-3.25 (High), 3.260-4.00 (Very High)

The data indicates that the immediate impact of performance knowledge is a clear strength, on which the participants were highly in agreement that it matters as evidenced by the highest mean rating value of 3.40 (SD=0.55). Accordingly, employees perceive knowledge as pivotal in augmenting their job performance. However, some of the issues relating to knowledge management are perceived to be lacking, with slightly lower mean scores than the grand mean of 3.30 (SD = 0.58). Particularly, the potential for learning (Mean = 3.29, SD = 0.51), regular investment in training and development (Mean = 3.23, SD = 0.68), knowledge channels for sharing (Mean = 3.29, SD = 0.61), and a focus on competence as an important driver of performance (Mean = 3.29, SD = 0.56) are revealed to be those areas that, while ranked relatively high, still do possess some potential for improvement.

These results emphasize the need to enhance knowledge acquisition opportunities, ensure unflinching investment in training, refine knowledge dissemination practice, and prioritize competence to underpin the organization's overall knowledge management.

Table 3. *Organizational Commitment*

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Tell friends that the organization is good to work for.	3.19	0.57	High
2. Personal values and the organization's values are very similar.	3.06	0.75	High
3. Proud to tell others of being part of the organization.	3.34	0.58	Very High
4. Willing to put in a great deal of extra effort to help the organization be successful.	3.34	0.63	Very High
5. Extremely glad in choosing to work in the organization rather than one of the other jobs considered at the time joined.	3.24	0.60	High

Overall	3.23	0.63	High
---------	------	------	------

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Low), 1.76-2.50 (Average), 2.51-3.25 (High), 3.260-4.00 (Very High)

The results show that there is a prevalent feeling of strong organizational commitment, with a mean overall score of 3.23 (SD = 0.63). This suggests a strong sense of dedication within the organization with employees demonstrating a high level of pride in their affiliation with the company and willingness to exert additional effort, both of which are categorically rated as "Very High" (Mean = 3.34). However, there are certain areas that require attention, in this instance pertaining to how employees think and advocate the organization's strengths to others while the intention to recommend the organization as an excellent place to work and personal and organizational values' alignment both have "High" Mean = 3.19 and 3.06, respectively), but they are below the threshold for the "Very High" category, meaning areas where there can be enhanced value alignment and stronger advocacy by the employees of the organization.

Table 4. Rewards

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Employees value tangible rewards.	3.17	0.65	High
2. Compensation benefits affect performance.	3.43	0.55	Very High
3. Employees appreciate salaries and benefits.	3.34	0.63	Very High
4. Provide opportunity for Promotion for performing employees.	3.14	0.83	High
5. Commendation by supervisor affects performance and commitment.	3.29	0.61	Very High
Overall	3.27	0.66	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Low), 1.76-2.50 (Average), 2.51-3.25 (High), 3.260-4.00 (Very High)

Based on the findings, it is evident that the overall perception of rewards is very high with a mean score of 3.27 (SD = 0.66). Noteworthy strengths encompass the positive influence of compensation benefits on performance (Mean = 3.43, SD = 0.55), the appreciation of salaries and benefits (Mean = 3.34, SD = 0.63), and the impact of commendation by supervisors on performance and commitment (Mean = 3.29, SD = 0.61), all of which fall under the category of "Very High." Conversely, aspects such as valuing tangible rewards (Mean = 3.17, SD = 0.65) and providing opportunities for promotion (Mean = 3.14, SD = 0.83) are rated as "High." This suggests positive perceptions while indicating the potential for further enhancement to elevate them to the "Very High" category.

Table 5. Skills

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Support employees to learn new skills.	3.23	0.72	High
2. Encourages employee skill flexibility to improve performance.	3.17	0.65	High
3. Capable of putting new skills to use within a short time.	3.03	0.65	High
4. Employees change work habits in response to changes in environment.	3.14	0.64	High
5. Factory is capable of meeting demand for new skills.	3.06	0.67	High
Overall	3.13	0.67	High

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Low), 1.76-2.50 (Average), 2.51-3.25 (High), 3.260-4.00 (Very High)

The analysis of the skill factor shows that all sub-factors are equally perceived as "High," with mean scores of 3.13 (SD=0.67). The best-rated statements show that the organization actively encourages employees to attain new skills (M=3.23, SD=0.72), promotes skill flexibility among employees to optimize performance (M=3.17, SD=0.65), and develops an atmosphere wherein employees are allowed to modify work habits in reaction to changes in the environment (M=3.14, SD=0.64). Potential areas for further development are the ability of the organization to satisfy the need for new skills (M=3.06, SD=0.67) and the ability to use new skills quickly (M=3.03, SD=0.65).

2. Level Of Job Involvement

Table 6. Job Involvement

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Complete work even if it takes more than required time without any extra salary.	3.09	0.69	High
2. Spend oneself in job related activities.	3.03	0.7	High
3. Keep engaged at work without bothering about happening to thyself.	3.03	0.71	High
4. Think about the work at the time of doing it.	3.26	0.5	Very High
5. Keep self-involved in my work.	3.31	0.52	Very High
Overall	3.14	0.62	High

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Low), 1.76-2.50 (Average), 2.51-3.25 (High), 3.260-4.00 (Very High)

The analysis reveals that job involvement is overall viewed as "High," with an overall mean score of 3.14 (SD = 0.62). The most highly rated statements pertain to employees being actively involved in their work (M=3.31, SD=0.52) and still thinking about their work even after they have completed it (M=3.26, SD=0.5). Improvement is needed in this critical area through the completion of work even if it requires more than the allotted time without additional compensation (M=3.09, SD=0.69), one's full commitment to job-related tasks (M=3.03, SD=0.7), and remaining on task at work without sacrificing personal well-being (M=3.03, SD=0.71). This indicates that although employees are very involved in their work, they are less likely to work overtime and sacrifice their personal lives, which shows a good work-life balance.

3. Effect of Attitude, Knowledge, Organizational Commitment, Reward, and Skills on Job Involvement

The examination of variable relationships as conducted using path coefficient tables generated by the Smart PLS-SEM tool. The tables provided path coefficients offering insights into the connections between critical variables: Attitude, Knowledge, Organizational Commitment, Reward, Skills, and Job Involvement. These coefficients denote the magnitude and direction of the impact of each independent variable on the dependent variables. Please refer to the Path Coefficient diagram provided below for further details.

Figure 1. Path Coefficient

Table 7. Path Coefficient of All Variables

Path	Attitude	Knowledge	Organizational Commitment	Reward	Skills	Job Involvement
Attitude	-	0.426	0.677	-	-	-0.072
Knowledge	-0.084	-	-0.055	-	0.101	-
Organizational Commitment	-	-	-	-	-	0.868
Reward	0.567	0.554	-0.217	-	0.532	0.749
Skills	-0.22	-	0.033	-	-	-

The table provided illustrate the path coefficients between key constructs: Attitude, Knowledge, Organizational Commitment, Reward, Skills, and Job Involvement, and how they influence Job Involvement. The path coefficients reveal the complex relationships among these variables.

Attitude

This has various impacts on different variables. It has a positive impact on Knowledge ($\beta=0.426$) and Organizational Commitment ($\beta=0.677$), indicating that employees having a good attitude are likely to participate in learning and be strongly committed to their organization. Furthermore, Attitude significantly positively influences Reward perception ($\beta=0.567$), reflecting that employees with a good attitude are inclined to enjoy and be driven by rewards. However, Attitude's effect on Skills is negative moderate ($\beta=-0.220$), and this can imply that a good attitude can not necessarily contribute to the acquisition of skills, possibly due to complacency or satisfaction with current skills. Lastly, Attitude has a weak negative relationship with Job Involvement ($\beta=-0.072$), indicating that shifts in attitude, if not managed, could slightly reduce how involved employees are in their work, highlighting the importance of fostering a consistently positive attitude to maintain high levels of job engagement

Knowledge

The data indicates that a positive attitude ($\beta=0.426$) has a significant impact on knowledge, implying that employees who approach their work with optimism are more likely to acquire and apply new knowledge. Additionally, knowledge has a modest positive effect on skills ($\beta=0.101$), showing that as employees accumulate knowledge, their skill levels tend to improve. However, it is worth

noting that knowledge has weak negative impact on both attitude ($\beta=-0.084$) and job involvement ($\beta=-0.055$). This suggests that while acquiring knowledge is generally beneficial, it may not always result in increased job involvement or a more positive attitude. This could be due to the complexities or challenges associated with new knowledge, which may not align with employees' immediate job roles or expectations.

Organizational commitment

This plays an important role in influencing various facets of employee behavior and attitudes within the workplace. It is notably influenced by attitude ($\beta=0.677$), signifying that employees who harbor a positive attitude toward their professional responsibilities are more predisposed to exhibit commitment to their employing organization. Said commitment, in turn, exerts a highly positive influence on job involvement ($\beta=0.868$), thereby serving as a critical catalyst for stimulating employee engagement and active participation in work-related initiatives whilst the impact of organizational commitment on skills is marginal ($\beta=0.033$), it remains a salient factor in driving job involvement, ability without a substantial contribution to skill development. Cultivating robust organizational commitment is imperative for ensuring elevated levels of job involvement, thereby intricately anchoring employees' dedication to their respective roles.

Reward

The reward system significantly influences various organizational factors and plays a pivotal role in shaping employee attitudes and behaviors. It strongly impacts attitude ($\beta=0.567$), indicating that effective reward systems can substantially enhance employees' outlook and satisfaction with their work environment. Moreover, reward has a positive influence on knowledge ($\beta=0.554$), which indicates that sufficiently rewarded workers are more inclined to learn and implement new knowledge. In addition, rewards have a very significant positive influence on skills ($\beta=0.532$), which suggests that proper reward of employees enhances their skill development, and therefore overall performance. In addition, the reward system is one of the significant drivers of job involvement ($\beta=0.749$), showing its essential influence in encouraging workers to become more involved in work. Briefly, well-designed reward, system increases employee satisfaction, induces learning and skill development, and encourages higher job involvement.

Skills

The skills have a direct impact on various organizational components. While they are positively influenced by knowledge ($\beta=0.101$), i.e., as employees acquire more knowledge, their skill levels tend to rise, the direct influence of skills on other variables is complicated. Skills have a slight positive effect on organizational commitment ($\beta=0.033$), suggesting that skill development can marginally contribute to employees' commitment to the organization. But the relationship between attitude and skills is negative and moderate ($\beta=-0.220$), indicating that workers can feel greater job complexity or pressure after gaining new skills and possibly have a more negative attitude. While the link between skills and job involvement is not delineated, skills influence job involvement indirectly by affecting reward and knowledge, suggesting that skill development is still a strong determinant of overall job engagement and performance.

Table 8. *Path Coefficient on the Effect of Attitude, Knowledge, Organizational Commitment, Reward, and Skills on Job Involvement*

Independent Variable	Path Coefficient	HO Decision	Interpretation
HO1. Attitude	-0.072	Accept	Weak negative relationship; changes in attitude slightly decrease job involvement.
HO2. Knowledge	-0.055	Accept	Weak negative relationship; knowledge slightly decreases job involvement.
HO3. Organizational Commitment	0.868	Reject	Very strong positive relationship; commitment significantly increases job involvement.
HO4. Reward	0.749	Reject	Strong positive relationship; rewards significantly enhance job involvement.
HO5. Skills	-0.22	Accept	Moderate negative relationship; higher skills slightly decrease job involvement.

Through path coefficient analysis, the complex interconnections among attitude, knowledge, organizational commitment, reward, and skills, and their combined influence on job involvement underscore the vital role of organizational commitment and reward systems in nurturing employee engagement.

Attitude

The path coefficient is -0.072, and the HO1 is accepted. This shows weak negative relationship, indicating that changes in attitude marginally decrease job involvement while the impact is minor; it underscores the importance of maintaining a positive attitude to prevent any potential decrease in job involvement.

Knowledge

The path coefficient is -0.055, and the HO2 is accepted. This result indicates weak negative relationship, suggesting that an increase in knowledge slightly decreases job involvement. This finding implies that while knowledge is valuable, it may not directly contribute to enhancing job involvement and could potentially reduce it if not aligned with job responsibilities.

Organizational Commitment

The path coefficient is 0.868, and the HO3 is rejected. The very strong positive relationship indicates that higher organizational commitment significantly increases job involvement. This underscores the critical role of fostering strong organizational commitment to enhance employee engagement and involvement in their work.

Reward

The path coefficient is 0.749, and the HO4 is rejected. This strong positive relationship suggests that rewards significantly enhance job involvement. Providing appropriate rewards is crucial for motivating employees and ensuring their active participation in job-related activities.

Skills

The path coefficient is -0.22, and the HO5 is accepted. This moderate negative relationship indicates that higher skill levels slightly decrease job involvement, possibly due to the increased complexity or demands associated with higher skill sets. This finding suggests that skill development should be carefully managed to ensure it leads to greater job involvement rather than reducing it.

The research shows that organizational commitment and rewards are crucial in boosting employees' job involvement. According to Mowday et al., (1982), a strong emotional bond with an organization significantly improves employee engagement and performance. Herzberg's two-factor

theory (1959) also emphasizes the importance of rewards and recognition as primary motivators for driving job involvement, a view supported by Shastri (2010) who stresses the significance of fair compensation in maintaining high levels of employee engagement.

On the other hand, the study indicates that skills and attitudes have a more intricate impact on job involvement. Dex and Smith (2011) suggest that underutilized skills can lead to reduced job satisfaction, which might explain the observed negative relationship between skills and job involvement. Additionally, Robbins (2013) and Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) point out that while positive attitudes can enhance organizational commitment, they do not always directly correlate with increased job involvement, suggesting the influence of other factors.

Knowledge was also identified as having a nuanced impact on job involvement while Camilleri (2012) and Ongori (2007) propose that well-informed and continuously developed employees are more likely to be engaged, the findings indicate that knowledge alone is insufficient for ensuring high job involvement. This suggests that knowledge needs to be combined with opportunities for application and growth to truly enhance engagement.

In summary, the findings are in line with existing literature, underscoring the significance of organizational commitment and rewards in driving job involvement, and shedding light on the more complex roles of skills, attitudes, and knowledge in influencing employee engagement.

Conclusions

The study concludes the following:

1. The respondents have a positive perception of the organization. It is surprising, especially considering the hazardous nature of the gas and oil business. The positive attitude is seen in the high to very high level of endorsement.
2. Among the various factors influencing this perception, Knowledge, Rewards, and Organizational Commitment stands out as the most highly endorsed while Skills and Attitude were the least extents.
3. Organizational Commitment and Rewards have strong and positive impacts on Job Involvement. These findings underscore the critical need to build strong commitment and rewarding employees in order to sustain high employee involvement.

4. Further, the study demonstrates the moderate effects of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude (KSA) on Job Involvement, with a slight decrease in job involvement associated with these factors.
5. The study's scope is limited by its concentration on a single organization and a specific set of variables, which may not fully capture the complexities of job involvement across diverse industries and cultural contexts. Additionally, the study's reliance on self-reported data which may be susceptible to bias, and its cross-sectional design constrain the ability to establish causal relationships between the variables.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following are recommended:

1. Improve Organizational Commitment

Employ techniques aimed at reinforcing employees' emotional tie to the company. This can be achieved through active engagement in decision-making processes and transparent communication of the organization's values.

2. Streamline Reward Systems

Ensure that rewards are not only competitive but also in line with employee expectations, offering a harmonious blend of financial incentives and avenues for career advancement and acknowledgment.

3. Invest in Knowledge Development

Establish continuous learning programs designed to empower employees to effectively apply their knowledge, thereby heightening their commitment to their roles.

4. Maximize Skill Utilization

Create opportunities for employees to undertake challenging tasks and receive advanced training, guaranteeing the full utilization of their skill sets and averting disengagement.

5. Cultivate a Positive work Culture

Foster a supportive and all-encompassing environment that augments overall employee contentment and engagement.

6. Expand Research Scope and Methodology

Foster further investigational studies spanning diverse industries and cultural contexts and contemplate longitudinal and/or mixed-method research to comprehend the dynamics of job involvement comprehensively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adheres to ethical standards in the collection, analysis, and presentation of data. The study was conducted with a commitment to ensuring that all participants' rights and privacy were respected throughout the research process. Participants were fully informed about the nature of the study, and their consent was obtained prior to participation. Confidentiality was maintained, and no personal or identifying information was disclosed in the findings.

The study relied on self-reported data, a method that while useful, presents certain limitations regarding potential biases. The researchers ensured that the data collection process was transparent and that participants could provide their responses freely without any coercion. The use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was aligned with best practices for ensuring the reliability and validity of the results. The researchers of this study acknowledge the limitations of focusing on a single organization, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings. However, the study was designed to ensure that the insights gained would contribute meaningfully to the field, particularly in understanding the dynamics of job involvement in high-risk industries like the oil and gas sector. Ethical dimensions were a fundamental part of the study, ensuring the validity and value of the study for both academic and practical ends.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to extend sincere gratitude to Dr. Michael B. Pasco for his exceptional guidance, insightful feedback, and steadfast support throughout the duration of this research. His expertise and mentorship were crucial in shaping the study's direction and enhancing its quality. The researchers also wish to express their deep appreciation to their friends, family, and classmates at the San Beda University - Graduate School of Business. Their support, fellowship, and unshakeable dedication to greatness have always been a steady source of strength and inspiration. This study is a testament to the collective efforts and support of these individuals.

Additionally, the researcher was deeply grateful to Schlumberger, WCM Operations Manager Ayman Al Ghazzawi, office mates, CCF Al Khobar and C1 Family for their support during the survey process. Special thanks also go to Mrs. Marify Rafol Sababan, her co-teachers at the American International School, Aziziyah, and KSA, whose encouragement and cooperation were invaluable. This research would not have been possible without the

contributions and support of these remarkable individuals, and the researcher profoundly thankful for their involvement.

REFERENCES

- Camilleri, E. (2012). Some antecedents of organizational attitude: Results from an information systems public sector organization. *Bank of Valletta Review*, 25, 1-29.
- Campbell, J. P. (1990). Modeling the performance prediction problem in industrial and organizational psychology. In M. D. Dunnette & L. M. Hough (Eds.), *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology* (2nd ed.), Vol. 1, 687-732. Consulting Psychologists Press.
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., & Nachreiner, F. (2017). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83(3), 379-390.
- Dex, S., & Smith, C. (2011). Effects of family-friendly policies on employee attitude: An analysis of the workplace employee relation survey. The Judge Institute of Management Studies Working Paper, wp20/2011, 1-36.
- Fishbein, M. (1975). Ajzen. i. (1975). Belief, attitude, intention and behavior: An introduction to theory and research, 181-202.
- Herzberg, F. (1966). *Work and the Nature of Man*. World Publishing Company.
- Judge, T. A., Thoresen, C. J., Bono, J. E., & Patton, G. K. (2001). *The job satisfaction–job performance relationship: A qualitative and quantitative review*. *Psychological Bulletin*, 127(3), 376-407. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.127.3.376>.
- Kanungo, R. N. (1982). Work alienation: An integrative approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, 91(1), 47–76.
- Kiazad, K., Avey, J. B., & Nimmo, R. (2019). The relationship between work attitudes, organizational commitment, and job involvement in high-risk industries. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 24(2), 255-268.
- Mowday, R. T., Porter, L. W., & Steers, R. M. (1982). *Employee-Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism, and Turnover*. Academic Press.
- Ongori, H. (2007). A review of the literature on employee turnover.
- Robbins, S. P. (2013). *Organizational behavior* (15th ed.) Pearson.
- Shastri, R. K. (2010). *Fair compensation and employee engagement: An empirical study*. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(10), 145-154. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v5n10p145>